

Extraction chromatographic method of thallium(III) with n-capric acid and its analytical applications

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The extraction chromatographic separation of Tl^{III} from several elements with n-capric acid coated on silica gel is reported. Tl^{III} is quantitatively extracted from 0.1 M ammonium acetate in the pH range 2.4–6.0. Tl^{III} is stripped with 0.01 M HCl and estimated spectrophotometrically. The effects of pH, stripping agents, flow rate on extraction and elution, and effect of diverse ions have been studied. Micro-amounts of Tl^{III} have been separated from various metal ions. The method permits sequential separation of Al^{III} , Ga^{III} , In^{III} and Tl^{III} from synthetic mixture.

The utility of carboxylic acids as extractant has become a subject of general interest¹. Bis(2-ethylhexyl)phosphoric acid (HDEHP)² and trioctylphosphine oxide (TOPO)³ have been used for the separation of Ga, In, Tl and Al. The solvent extraction behaviour of Tl^{III} with liquid cation exchanger has been reported⁴. Most of the reported methods lack in selectivity. n-Capric acid as extractant, has been used to study the chromatographic behaviour of U^{VI} ⁵ and Zr^{IV} ⁶ but studies of Tl^{III} with n-capric acid has not yet been reported. This paper presents the results of systematic studies of Tl^{III} on silica gel column coated with n-capric acid and its sequential separation from Al^{III} , Ga^{III} and In^{III} .

Results and Discussion

The extraction behaviour of Tl^{III} with capric acid was studied at different pHs keeping its concentration constant. The percentage of extraction increased with increasing pH and became quantitative in the pH range 2.4–6.0. Flow rates at 0.5, 1.0 and 1.5 ml min⁻¹ showed the complete retention of Tl^{III} on the column. Nitrate, sulphate, perchlorate and tartrate did not interfere but chloride and oxalate did. Tl^{III} was quantitatively stripped with 0.5–1 M HNO_3 , 0.01–0.05 M HCl, 0.5–1 M H_2SO_4 , 1–2 M NaCl and 1–2 M $HClO_4$ from the column. A 0.01 M HCl gave the best stripping, hence it was used for all the experiment.

Breakthrough capacity (the amount of ions which can be taken up by column without any leakage) was determined with respect to Tl^{III} at pHs 2.5 and 4.8. Ion exchange column (1–2 cm) was prepared with 1.01 g of exchanger. Tl^{III} solution (1.05 mg ml⁻¹) in 0.1 M ammonium acetate at the desired pH (pH 2.5 and 4.9) was passed through the column at a flow rate of 0.4 ml min⁻¹. The leakage of Tl^{III} started at pH 2.5 and 4.8 after passing 8.4 and 26.2 mg of the Tl^{III} respectively.

Separation of Tl^{III} from binary mixtures : Metal ions like Cr^{III} , Co^{II} , Ni^{II} , Zn^{II} , Cd^{II} , Ag^I , Pt^{IV} , Au^{III} and U^{VI} were not extracted at pH 2.5. Tl^{III} was selectively extracted and any diverse ions present passed with the mobile phase. The retained Tl^{III} was stripped with 0.01 M HCl (14 ml) with 99% recovery. Al^{III} , Ga^{III} , In^{III} , Pb^{II} , Hg^{II} , Bi^{III} , Zr^{IV} and Th^{IV} were extracted with Tl^{III} . However, their interferences were removed by exploiting the differences in stripping behaviour. The separation of Tl^{III} from any one of the above elements was done by passing the mixture at pH 5.0. Diverse ion was stripped first with 0.05 M HNO_3 (20 ml), later thallium with 0.01 M HCl (14 ml). The separation of Tl^{III} from Fe^{III} and Zr^{IV} was performed at pH 2.5, both being extracted. Fe^{III} was stripped with 0.02 M H_2SO_4 (30 ml), Zr^{IV} with 4 M HNO_3 (12.5 ml) and Tl^{III} with 0.01 M HCl (1 ml). When a binary mixture of Tl^{III} along with Th^{IV} was passed at pH 4.5, both were extracted. However, Tl^{III} was stripped first with 0.5 M NaCl, then Th^{IV} with 1 M HNO_3 (12 ml). In all cases most of the elements from eluted solution were determined spectrophotometrically.

Separation of Tl^{III} from multicomponent mixtures : The technique was applied to separate Tl^{III} from group of elements which are extracted with capric acid under identical conditions.

A mixture of Pb^{II} , Hg^{II} and Tl^{III} was passed through the column at pH 5.5, when all the elements were extracted. Pb^{II} was stripped first with water, then Hg^{II} with 0.05 M HNO_3 and finally Tl^{III} with 0.01 M HCl.

A mixture of Cr^{III} , Al^{III} , Fe^{III} and Tl^{III} was passed through the column at pH 3.5. Cr^{III} passed through the mobile phase. Al^{III} was stripped with distilled water, Fe^{III} with 0.02 M H_2SO_4 and finally Tl^{III} with 0.01 M HCl.

A mixture containing U^{VI} , Hg^{II} , Tl^{III} and Zr^{IV} was passed through the column at pH 4.8. U^{VI} passed through, Hg^{II} was

Note

Table 1. Separation of Tl^{III} from multicomponent mixtures*

Tl^{III} taken = 40 µg, Column = 1 × 8.5 cm, Flow rate = 0.5 ml min⁻¹

Sl. no.	Cation	Wt. added/ (Recovered), µg	Rel. error %	Eluent used	Eluent vol., ml
1.	Pb ^{II}	1420 (1410)	-0.70	H ₂ O	30
	Hg ^{II}	1220 (1230)	+0.82	0.05 M HNO ₃	24
	Tl ^{III}	40 (39.6)	-1.00	0.01 M HCl	14
2.	Cr ^{III}	3100 (3080)	-0.65	-	-
	Al ^{III}	55 (54.8)	-0.36	H ₂ O	30
	Fe ^{III}	50 (49.5)	+1.00	0.02 M H ₂ SO ₄	15
	Tl ^{III}	40 (39.9)	-0.25	0.01 M HCl	16
3.	U ^{VI}	502 (500)	-0.40	-	-
	Hg ^{II}	2450 (2480)	+1.22	0.05 M HNO ₃	25
	Tl ^{III}	40 (39.8)	-0.50	0.01 M HCl	15
	Zr ^{IV}	150 (149)	-0.67	4 M HNO ₃	15
4.	Al ^{III}	55 (54.6)	-0.73	H ₂ O	28
	In ^{III}	3100 (3080)	-0.66	0.01 M H ₂ SO ₄	20
	Ga ^{III}	25 (25.3)	+1.20	0.05 M HNO ₃	14
	Tl ^{III}	40 (39.9)	-0.25	0.01 M HCl	16

*Average of five determinations.

stripped with 0.05 M HNO₃, then Tl^{III} with 0.01 M HCl and finally Zr^{IV} with 4 M HNO₃.

In sequential separation of Al^{III}, Ga^{III}, In^{III} and Tl^{III}, the mixture was passed through the column at pH 5.0, when all the elements were extracted. Al^{III} was recovered first with water, then In^{III} with 0.01 M H₂SO₄, Ga^{III} with 0.05 M HNO₃ and finally Tl^{III} with 0.01 M HCl.

In all these separations, most of the metal ions in eluent were determined spectrophotometrically and the results are given in Table 1. The overall time required for extraction and separation does not exceed 2 h. The method is repro-

ducible with an accuracy of ±1.5%. The proposed method is very simple, rapid and selective in comparison to other methods reported earlier.

Experimental

An Elico LI-120 pH meter, ECIL GS 5700 A spectrophotometer and a chromatographic column with a glass wool plug at the bottom were used.

Capric acid (Woko Chemical Industries, Japan) was used as liquid cation exchanger. A solution of Tl^{III} was prepared by dissolving of TlNO₃ in deionised water, oxidised to Tl^{III}

by bromine water, and standardised complexometrically with EDTA⁷. A solution containing 40 $\mu\text{g ml}^{-1}$ of Tl^{III} was prepared by dilution. All other metal ions and reagents were of analytical grade.

Silica gel (BDH, 60–120 mesh) was dried at 120° for 2 h and rendered hydrophobic by exposing to the vapour of dimethyl dichlorosilane in nitrogen atmosphere for 3 h. It was washed with methanol and dried at 100°⁸. Hydrophobic gel was coated with n-capric acid taken in benzene. Evaporation of benzene was done in rotary vacuum evaporator. Excess organic reagent was washed with 2 M HCl. 1 g of silica gel can take up about 0.9 ml of capric acid.

The exchange capacity was determined at different temperatures by shaking 25 M NaCl (50 ml) with dry exchanger (1 g) for 10 h in hot-cum-cold bath and titrating the solution (25 ml) with standard alkali. The exchange capacity of the exchanger was found to be 1.62 meq of H^+ /g at 25°.

General procedure : A slurry of silica gel coated with capric acid was transferred to a chromatographic column and the bed height was maintained at 7.5 cm. Solution containing 40 μg of Tl^{III} was made to 0.1 M in ammonium acetate in a total volume of 10 ml and its pH was adjusted to 2.4–5.5 by 0.5 M HNO_3 . The solution was passed through the pretreated column at a flow rate of 0.5 ml min^{-1} . After

extraction, Tl^{III} was stripped with mineral acids. Seven fractions (each of 2 ml) were collected and thallium from each fraction was determined spectrophotometrically as the thallium-rhodamine complex in benzene at 560 nm⁹.

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